

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Solanum ferox* Linn

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Solanum ferox linn (Fam. Solanaceae), a moderately sized (2-4') evergreen shrub, grows wildy in Garhwal, Madras, Bihar, Orissa, Assam, Ceylon and China. The roots, leaves, stems, flowers, fruits and seeds have been widely used in the indigenous system of medicine for sore throat, cough, asthma, chest pains, dropsy and rheumatism¹. The chemical analysis of the seed oil and the alkaloidal content of the fruits of this plant were reported earlier^{2,3}. An examination of the seed oil of *Solanum ferox* Linn has further revealed the presence of solanocarpone (0.036%) and carpesterol (0.073%).

Air-dried powdered seeds (1500 g.) were soxhletted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The petroleum extract on concentration gave a yellow coloured oil (2.7%) which was purified by treating it successively with Fuller's earth and activated charcoal. On allowing to stand for 15 days, the oil deposited a yellow sticky mass, which was filtered, washed successively with petroleum and benzene to remove the adhering fatty material. The crude product was repeatedly extracted with warm ethanol. On concentrating and keeping the ethanolic extract overnight in a refrigerator, a brown amorphous powder separated which on repeated crystallisation from hot absolute alcohol afforded cream coloured microscopic needles (0.55 g.); m.p. 78° (Found: C, 68.45; H, 8.76; Calc. for C₂₈H₄₂O₇: C, 68.57; H, 8.57%).

The compound shows all the characteristic properties of $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ unsaturated lactones, and was characterized as solanocarpone⁴ from its physical and chemical properties.

After removal of the lactone, the oil was saponified with ethanolic potassium hydroxide in the usual manner. On separating and keeping the unsaponifiable matter in a refrigerator, a white solid separated, which on repeated crystallisation from methanol afforded shining white plates (1.1 g.); m.p. 248° (Found: C, 78.69; H, 9.42; Calc. for C₃₆H₅₄O₄: C, 78.54; H, 9.8%).

The substance was fairly soluble in boiling ethanol and methanol, sparingly soluble in hot benzene, chloroform, acetone, ethyl ether and petroleum ether. It developed

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2. Garg and Gupta, *Fette. Seifen. Anstrichmittel*, 1966, **68**, 449.
3. Gupta and Garg, *Naturwiss.*, 1966, **54**, 108.
4. Gupta and Dutta, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 95.

reddish purple colour in Liebermann-Burchard reaction and was identified as carpesterol⁴ through the formation of its acetyl derivative, m.p. 193° (Found: C, 77.24; H, 9.62; Calc. for C₃₈H₅₆O₅: C, 77.02; H, 9.46%) and benzoyl derivative, m.p. 216°. (Found: C, 78.96; H, 8.69; Calc. for C₄₃H₅₈O₅: C, 78.89; H, 8.86%).

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